
A Data Visualization Platform for Analyzing Social Relations in 19th-century Alegrete

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Abstract

This work aims to present the development process of *Tertúlia*, a platform that offers data visualization tools to support History researchers in studying baptism records from the Nossa Senhora da Conceição Aparecida do Alegrete Chapel. The platform focuses on uncovering social relationships that can be inferred from these historical registries.

Alegrete is located in the far south of Brazil, in the western part of the former Rio Grande de São Pedro province, near the present-day border with Argentina and Uruguay. Following the Portuguese expansion south of the Ibicuí River in 1812, a chapel was established in the area but was burned down later that year by forces led by General José Artigas. It was rebuilt in 1816 on the banks of the Ibirapuitã River. At the time, the region was inhabited by Charrúa and Guarani Indigenous groups and was contested by the Portuguese and Spanish empires. After the Cisplatine War (1825–1828), the territory was incorporated into the Brazilian Empire. The area became known for its extensive cattle production, which supplied the salted meat processing industries along the coast of Rio Grande do Sul, primarily serving Brazil's domestic market. In 1831, Alegrete was officially established as a city, based on the chapel's jurisdiction (Farinatti 2007, 69).

As a border region that experienced multiple conflicts during the period in question, the local elite of Alegrete sought to maintain its power by expanding its networks of influence. In this context, both horizontal and vertical reciprocity networks played a crucial role in forging ties that offered security, protection, mutual aid, and opportunities for social mobility - factors that were central to the structuring of local power. Baptism served as one means of establishing these bonds, enabling the formation of *compadrazgo* relationships, which could be strategically employed as part of family-based social strategies.

The projects coordinated by historian Luís Augusto Farinatti of the Federal University of Santa Maria aimed to investigate the roles of individuals in the 19th-century society of Alegrete. Drawing on digitized images of baptism records from FamilySearch - specifically four books from the chapel dated between 1816 and 1850 - a total of 7,845 records were analyzed. The information was cataloged in a standardized format using an Excel spreadsheet. Because the source material followed the structure outlined in the Primeiras Constituições do Arcebisado da Bahia (Vide 1707), the records were relatively uniform, which facilitated data organization in a database and opened up multiple avenues for research.

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Given the complexity of the relationships among individuals found in these records, we identified data visualization techniques as a valuable tool. Such techniques empower users to explore and analyze data - even when they have not yet formulated specific research questions - and they accelerate analyses that would otherwise be slower and less effective (Munzner 2014, 2–3). To address this need, we developed *Tertúlia*, a web application that consolidates the previously collected data, offering enhanced standardization along with features for search, disambiguation, and analysis through visualization tools. The primary motivation for building a dedicated platform was to integrate all visualizations directly with the underlying database records, thereby reducing reliance on multiple separate tools and improving research productivity. The platform emerged from an interdisciplinary collaboration between historians and computer scientists.

The first step in building the platform involved extracting data from Farinatti's spreadsheets and storing it in a database created with MongoDB, which was chosen for its flexible data structure. After extraction, the data was standardized to eliminate synonymous terms, allowing for more consistent records and enabling efficient queries that enhance the user experience for researchers. The database was organized into collections: one for individual data ("People"), another for inferred connections such as godparenthood and *compadrazgo* ("Relationships"), and a third for baptism details, including date and source ("Baptisms"). All data extraction and transformation scripts were written in TypeScript and executed in a Node.js environment.

To make the extracted and stored data accessible to users, the platform's back end was developed using TypeScript and Node.js. It retrieves data from the database and serves it to the front end according to three levels of user permissions: administrators, maintainers, and viewers. Viewers can only perform read operations, while maintainers are also able to add, edit, and delete records. Administrators have the additional ability to manage user accounts and assign permissions. This permission structure is essential, as the data is required to remain private.

With the data structured and accessible, the focus shifted to developing the front end of the application, with particular attention to visual analysis tools such as timelines, radar charts for comparisons, and node-edge diagrams that represent the network of relationships within the society. The front end was built using the Vue.js framework, with visualizations implemented using JavaScript and the HTML Canvas element.

Over time, individuals may have been more or less frequently chosen as godparents, depending on various factors such as their power and influence. To support the analysis of this variation, a timeline visualization was developed. It displays the frequency of appearances of a specific person or couple as godparents over the years and allows for comparisons between different individuals in this regard.

Another way of analyzing the evolution of appearances in the baptisms of a person is via the ranking tool. It creates a ranking of the top 20 people with most appearances during a given interval of years, also showing year by year the updates in the positions of the ranking.

Researchers may also want to compare different individuals based on their own characteristics or those of their related people. For instance, they might be interested in identifying which person has the most connections to the military. To facilitate such comparisons, a radar chart visualization was developed, allowing for single or multiple selections and superimposing the data into a single chart.

The primary visualization tool is the node-edge diagram, which allows for the analysis and exploration of relationships between individuals. By selecting specific people, users can visualize their network through three key configurations: degree (depth of relational layers), relationship types (such as godparenthood, *compadrazgo*, and marriage), and date range. These options provide both a snapshot and a temporal view of an individual's social net-

work. Additional customization options enable the highlighting of relationship types by drawing edges in different styles and colors based on their nature. Beyond the graphical network representation, the platform also offers key social network analysis metrics, including network density, transitivity, and node centrality and betweenness.

In addition to the data visualization tools, the platform offers profile pages for each individual in the database. These pages detail their appearances in the registries and list the people connected to them, organized by the type of relationship. To access these profiles, an advanced search feature is available, allowing users to filter by race, legal status, and prestige indicators such as titles. Furthermore, to consolidate profiles from different records and appearances, the platform includes a disambiguation tool that allows users to link profiles of the same individual.

These features simplify the identification of aspects of social networks that would otherwise be time-consuming and challenging to analyze. Additionally, the visual nature of the representations makes relationships more tangible and easier to understand. In this way, the *Tertúlia* platform has significantly enhanced the analysis of social networks in 19th-century Alegrete, providing researchers with deeper insights and a broader understanding of the social dynamics of the time.

One of the primary applications of the platform has been the study of women from the elite of the parish of Alegrete. These women were identified with the title of "Dona" in the parish records, a designation granted by the local priest. The research focused on baptismal records as the primary source to examine the role of these women as godmothers in the local chapel. Using this data and applying Social Network Analysis methodology, it became possible to reconstruct the relationship networks connecting these women, thereby enabling the investigation of their social profiles and characteristics.

The platform's effectiveness was evaluated using traditional software validation methods, including the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) and the System Usability Scale (SUS). The questionnaires were administered to both active users (who also contributed to defining the platform's features) and potential users (who had restricted access), all of whom were History researchers with varying educational backgrounds and research focuses. The results confirmed the platform's utility, with a SUS score of 89/100 - well above the typical threshold of 68, which is considered good (Brooke 1996, 4-7). Additionally, the platform received the following scores on the UEQ: 2.73/3 in attractiveness, 1.75/3 in perspicuity, 2.50/3 in efficiency, 2.05/3 in dependability, 2.90/3 in stimulation, and 2.35/3 in novelty.

Due to the fact that the data used in the platform was collected by individuals not directly involved in this project, the current version of the platform is private. However, the platform itself is not specifically tied to the Alegrete baptism records. As a result, it can be expanded to incorporate data from other sources, which could eventually allow the platform to be made publicly accessible.

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